

AI IN EDUCATION: HOW TOOLS LIKE DUOLINGO, QUILLBOT, GRAMMARLY, AND CHATGPT ARE TRANSFORMING LANGUAGE LEARNING.

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Abstract

This thesis demonstrated how recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have significantly impacted various aspects of society, including education. AI technologies, such as Duolingo, Quillbot, Grammarly, and ChatGPT, are transforming language acquisition and communication skills development. Duolingo, a mobile-assisted language learning app, enhances students' skills in speaking, writing, reading, and listening through a gamified platform with progressive assignments. Quillbot, an AI-powered rewriting tool, helps users enhance text by offering various modes for maintaining meaning and improving formality.

Grammarly provides comprehensive writing feedback by identifying errors in grammar, spelling, and usage, serving both students and educators. ChatGPT, a generative pre-trained transformer developed by OpenAI, offers human-like responses and supports interactive learning environments with realistic dialogues. These AI tools collectively contribute to more dynamic, personalized, and efficient language learning experiences.

Key words: ChatGPT, mobile applications, Artificial Intelligence, OpenAI.

Introduction.

Artificial intelligence has advanced significantly in recent years and is now ingrained in many facets of society. It is distinguished by its capacity to simulate human intelligence. AI is being investigated more and more in the field of education as a potential tool to help and improve language acquisition, especially in the growth of students' communication abilities. AI has the ability to provide dynamic, adaptive, and customized learning experiences that are tailored to the requirements and interests of specific students. (Rusmiyanto, Huriati, Fitriani, Tyas, Rofi'I & Sari, 2023).

Nowadays, a lot of mobile applications are operated with AI, for example, Duolingo, Quillbot, Grammarly, ChatGbt have been widely used in English language teaching. Duolingo is one of the mobile assisted language learning application which helps students to improve their target foreign language skills, such as speaking, writing, reading, listening, vocabulary and grammar. Being

first launched by Severin Hacker and Luis Von Ahn in 2012, it has been developed as a commercial platform for language learners. Every level on Duolingo includes a range of assignments that need four distinct English learning skills and range in difficulty from beginner to advanced.

By using this particular app, students' vocabulary has increased, their ability to write simple phrases has improved, and it has proven to be helpful in supporting learners as they expand their vocabulary. (Sakkir & Syamsuddin, 2023; Purwanto & Syafryadin, 2023). Additionally, Munday (2016) describes Duolingo as a contemporary game. Word transcription, translation, and pronunciation are mostly emphasized in the program. In order to encourage and assist pupils, it also incorporates gamification elements.

Literature review

Quillbot is an AI powered bot which helps users to rewrite the sentences effortlessly. Quillbot provides a wide range of different modes ranging from maintaining the original meaning of the text and making it unique to altering it to look more formal to the audience if it is required. Assisting authors in finding suitable synonyms and improving the intelligibility of the given content, Quillbot is a great way of time saving for all users. Quillbot has gained popularity among millions of users worldwide, including students, writers, bloggers, and businesses, due to its extensive vocabulary and user-friendly interface. (Abdelli, 2023; Nguyen, 2023; Fitria, 2021).

One of the automatic writing evaluation app and computer software is Grammarly. It is an effective tool provides feedback for both students and teachers in their writing classes. (Bailey & Lee 2020; Ghufon & Rosyida 2018). According to the grammarly website, Grammarly identifies mistakes in many aspects of the language, such as grammar, spelling, punctuation, lexicon, word usage and even for plagiarism check. Currently, (2023) there are over 30 million active users of the software.

ChatGPT or Generative pre-trained transformer is one of the latest AI based chatbots which provides human resembling responses to the prompt. It was developed by Open AI and made available in November 2022. (Kohnke, Moorhouse & Zou, 2023). Baskara and Mukarto (2023) demonstrated that ChatGPT is trained on vast amount of text to realistically simulate human like conversations. It is capable of producing text without grammatical mistakes, making it not only coherently but also semantically relevant to the question being asked..

With its unique features of text-generation, ChatGPT is an effective tool for producing instructional materials and designing interactive learning environments. The model's capacity to produce realistic dialogues can provide learners with examples of real-world language use. (Zou et al, 2023).

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the integration of artificial intelligence into language education represents a significant advancement in enhancing learning experiences. Tools like Duolingo, Quillbot, Grammarly, and ChatGPT offer diverse functionalities that cater to various aspects of language acquisition, from vocabulary expansion and writing improvement to interactive practice and personalized feedback. Each application leverages AI's capacity to adapt and respond to individual learning needs, demonstrating the potential for these technologies to support and enrich language education. As these AI-driven tools continue to evolve, they are likely to play an increasingly pivotal role in shaping the future of language learning, making it more accessible, effective, and engaging for students worldwide. The continued development and adoption of such technologies promise to further transform how learners acquire and master new languages.

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